

SUN'IY INTELEKTNING TIL TAFAKKURIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellektning inson tafakkuriga ta'siri, yaxshi va yomon tomonlari tahlil qilinadi. Sun'iy intellekt yordamida bilim olish va ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash holatlarining tezligi va samaradorligi ko'rib chiqiladi hamda sun'iy intellekt insonning ijodiy va tanqidiy fikrlashiga qanday ta'sir o'tkazishi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, inson tafakkuri, ijodiy fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, bilim olish, qaror qabul qilish, Chatgpt.

Abstract: In this article, the impact of artificial intelligence on human thinking, its positive and negative aspects are analyzed. The speed and efficiency of knowledge acquisition and data processing with the help of artificial intelligence are examined, and how artificial intelligence affects human creative and critical thinking is discussed.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, human thinking, creative thinking, critical thinking, knowledge acquisition, decision making, Chatgpt.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется влияние искусственного интеллекта на человеческое мышление, а также его положительные и отрицательные стороны. Рассматривается скорость и эффективность усвоения знаний и обработки данных с помощью искусственного интеллекта, а также обсуждается, как искусственный интеллект влияет на творческое и критическое мышление человека.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, человеческое мышление, творческое мышление, критическое мышление, приобретение знаний, принятие решений, Chatgpt.

Hozirgi texnologiyalar davrida sun'iy intellekt alohida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. U inson ongi bajaradigan deyarli har bir ishni qilishga (hissiyotdan boshqa) qodir bir aqlli, raqamli texnologiya hisoblanadi. Ong bilan bog'liqligini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, bu, albatta, inson tafakkuriga o'z ta'sirini o'tkazmay qolmaydi.

Sun'iy intellektning yorqin namunalaridan biri – Chatgpt bo'lib, u o'zida bor bo'lgan ma'lumotlar bazasidan foydalangan holda insonlarning har qanday savoliga javob berish xususiyatiga ega. Ko'pchilikning sirdoshi aylangan chatgpt, har qanday tilda ma'lumotlar qabul qilib, ularni qayta ishlay olishi uning yutuqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Sun'iy intellekt muammosi ko'p yillar davomida turli bahs-munozaralarga sabab bo'lib kelmoqda. Bu mavzu quyidagi olimlar tomonidan o'rganilgan: Rahman A., Raj A., Tomy P., & Hameed M.S., Ansari S.R. & Qamari I.N. va boshqalar.

Hozirgi kunga kelib sun'iy intellekt hayotimizning turli jabhalarida o'zining ma'lum bir o'rniga ega bo'lib bormoqda, inson va til tafakkuri ham shu jumladandir. Bu mavzu turli olimlar tomonidan turlicha tahlil qilingan. "The rising pervasiveness of

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led applied linguists to combine it with language teaching and learning processes... integration of AI techniques such as natural language processing (NLP), natural language understanding (NLU), and automatic speech recognition (ASR) allows tools developed through them to be more appropriate in language learning platforms as they comprehend and process human-computer interaction. (Rahman A., Raj A., Tomy P., & Hameed M.S., 2024). A comprehensive bibliometric and content analysis of artificial intelligence in language learning: tracing between the years 2017 and 2023). Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, NLP (tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash), NLU (tabiiy tilni tushunish) va ASR (avtomatik nutqni tanish) kabi texnologiyalar inson hamda sun'iy intellekt o'zaro ta'sirini yaxshilab, til tafakkurining yaxshilanishiga yordam beradi.

“The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has the potential to significantly enhance students' cognitive learning outcomes ... revealing key themes, influential institutions, and collaborative networks, while also highlighting ethical concerns and the need for responsible implementation.” (Ansari S.R., & Qamari I.N., 2025). Artificial intelligence and students' cognitive learning outcomes with bibliometric and content analysis for future research agenda). Bu olimlar fikridan shuni takidlash joizki, sun'iy intellektning ta'limda qo'llanilishi o'quvchi va talabalarning kognitiv qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashga yordam berishi bilan birga, undan to'g'ri yo'lda hamda oqilona foydalanilmasa turli salbiy muammolarga sabab bo'ladi. Sun'iy intellekt ta'lim jarayonini yengillatish uchun foydali vosita hisoblanadi. Lekin, undan to'g'ri yo'lda, ya'ni yaxshi maqsadda foydalanmasak unga qaramlik yuzaga kelib, inson hayotining har sohasida unga tayanib ish qilish, o'z fikri bo'lmasligi yoki ma'lum bir mavzuda o'z fikrini erkin bayon eta olmaslik kabi jiddiy muammolarga olib keladi.

“The incorporation of AI offers learners personalized, interactive and adaptive language learning experiences that cater to individuals' needs and preferences.” (Huang W., Hew K.F., & Fryer L.K., 2023). The impact of artificial intelligence on learner engagement and personalized feedback in language learning: A systematic review). Sun'iy intellekt har bir o'rganuvchi insonning ehtiyojlarini aniqlay oladi va moslasha oladi, til o'rganish jarayonini ham osonlashtiradi.

Ingliz nazariyotchi-fizigi, ilm-fan targ'ibotchisi Stiven Xoking fikricha, sun'iy tafakkur taraqqiyoti kelajakda insoniyat tanazzuliga sabab bo'ladi. Olim sun'iy tafakkurning bu zaylda Joriy etilishi odamlar ahvolini asta-sekin yomonlashtiradi, deb hisoblaydi. Chunki, bunday evolyusiyaviy sharoitlarda inson yashab qolish uchun doimiy kurashda bo'ladi va bu jarayon, albatta, uni halokatga olib keladi. (Asrorova M.U., 47-b.)

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, sun'iy intellekt ilmiy nuqtai nazardan insonning til va tafakkur jarayonlariga kompleks ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi ko'p funksiyali kognitiv omil sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Bir so'z bilan aytganda, ilmiy tadqiqotlar va olimlar fikri shuni ko'rsatadiki, sun'iy intellektdan haddan tashqari foydalanish mustaqil va tanqidiy fikrlash darajasining sezilarli darajada sustlashuviga olib kelishi mumkin. Shu sababli sun'iy intellektdan ongli va muvozanatli ravishda foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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